

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF BISTABLE ENERGY HARVESTING BASED ON SILICONE DIELECTRIC ELASTOMER GENERATORS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a concept of bistable dielectric elastomer generator (DEG) and investigates its performance via numerical simulations. Whereas resonant DEG designs are largely used to achieve large convertible energy density over specific frequency ranges, bistability represents a potential alternative approach, suitable to scavenge energy over broad low-frequency ranges. In contrast to resonant designs, which demand for large inertia and are thus hard to down-scale, bistability might be an enabling solution for low-frequency harvesting at small scales. In this work, we study a DEG made of silicone. We first develop an electro-mechanical model of the system, based on established approaches and experimentally validated material properties. We then use the model to compare the performance of a monostable resonant implementation of the system and a bistable one, proving that the bistable system can potentially provide significantly higher convertible energy densities in a broad range of excitation conditions.

Keywords: dielectric elastomer, energy harvesting, bistable, generator

1 INTRODUCTION

Dielectric elastomers (DEs) are highly stretchable soft polymeric materials, which can be used as dielectric media in variable capacitance electrostatic transducers [1]. In the field of energy harvesting, DE generators (DEGs) might represent an enabling technology for different applications, covering a power range spanning several orders of magnitudes [2]. Proposed DEG applications range from energy recovery from human motion [3],

where highly compact lightweight generators are required, to large-scale ocean wave energy harvesting [4, 5], which demands for resilient corrosion-resistant transducers, able to efficiently work at low frequencies in the presence of highly-variable sea states.

The maximum energy that a DEG can convert increases monotonically with the maximum stretch it reaches [6]. On this end, the inherent stiffness of DE materials limits the deformations that a DEG can achieve in the presence of a given excitation force, and thus the energy that it can convert. This holds especially true in the case of relatively stiff DEs, such as silicone. Compared to softer materials, such as acrylics [5], is more reliable and offers better potential for industrialisation, but it features larger elastic modulus, which, to date, has significantly limited its application to energy harvesting [7]. To compensate for the material stiffness (even in the case of soft acrylic DEGs [5]) and match the DEG response with the excitation, in literature resonant designs have been pursued, in which the DE stiffness is partly balanced out by providing the system with sufficient inertia, so as to match its natural frequency with the one of the excitation [5, 8]. Because target mechanical energy sources (e.g., human motion, sea waves) feature low frequencies on the order $10^{-1} - 10^1$ Hz, DEG systems typically require large inertia to achieve resonance, making them difficult to down-scale. Moreover, resonant DEG systems often experiment a drop in performance when they work off-resonance or in the presence of broadband excitation [8].

In this paper, we analyse a concept of bistable DEG, which is potentially able to convert large amounts of energy over a broad range of excitation conditions, by taking advantage of large deformations induced by bistable jumps between a couple of stable equilibrium configurations. Whereas bistability has been largely

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investigated in the context of energy harvesting via piezoelectric or electromagnetic transducers [9], its application in DEG systems is still unexplored.

We make reference to a known DEG system based on an agonist-antagonist layout comprising two conically-deformed DEG membranes [10] made of silicone DE. This system can be either provided with a monostable response (oscillating above a single equilibrium position), or combined with a negative-rate biasing spring (NBS) which renders the DEG response bistable. We propose a model of the DEG system based on established and validated lumped-parameter energetically-consistent modelling approaches for DEs [11]. We use the model to compare the performance of a resonant monostable implementation of the system (obtained introducing a large moving mass in the system) and a bistable implementation, in the presence of prescribed excitation forces. We prove that the bistable implementation bears the potential to overperform the resonant one in the low frequency range (where resonant designs are made unfeasible by the demand for very large inertia) and in a broad range of excitation force magnitudes.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Sect. 2 introduces the system layout and mathematical model. Sect. 3 presents the results of numerical simulations. Sect. 4 presents the conclusions.

2 SYSTEM LAYOUT AND MODELLING

2.1 Bistable agonist-antagonist cone DEG

We set our attention on a DEG system consisting of a pair of DEG units in agonist-antagonist configuration (Fig. 1). The units feature a so-called cone DEG layout [12], and they are built by pre-stretching circular DE membranes in-plane (Fig. 1a), connecting them to a pair of rigid frames (an outer ring with radius r_o and an inner disc with radius r_i), and pre-loading them off-plane, one against the other (Fig. 1b). Each DE membrane consists in a stack of n_l electrode-covered DE layers, electrically connected in parallel. We denote t_0 the unstretched thickness of the single DE layers, and λ_p the in-plane equibiaxial pre-stretch. The central disc has mass m (assumed much larger than the elastomer mass) and is free to move along the axis. Monostable implementations of this architecture have been studied in the past [10], in which an excitation force F_{exc} applied on the moving disc causes a cyclic deformation of the DEGs. Such excitation can be either provided by mounting the DEG on a moving frame and exploiting inertial forces generated on the mass m , or by coupling the disc to a source of force (e.g. fluid current). Here, we study a bistable implementation of the system, in which the DEGs are coupled to a NBS rendered via a set of linear springs, pre-compressed in a direction perpendicular to the cone DEGs axis, and connected to the moving disc. If the NBS stiffness is sufficiently large, the resulting system has an unstable equilibrium position (where both DEGs are equally deformed) and two symmetrical stable

equilibrium points (above and below the unstable equilibrium). Practical compact implementations of NBSs might be obtained using buckled beams [13].

Electrical energy generation is achieved by suitably varying the voltage applied on the DEGs as a function of deformation, according to well-known harvesting cycles [2] (see Sect. 2.2.1).

2.2 Dynamic model

The dynamics of the DEG in the presence of an external excitation force F_{exc} is described in a lumped fashion by the following equation:

$$m\ddot{x} + F_e + F_v + F_b = F_{exc}, \quad (1)$$

where x is the axial displacement of the moving disc from the equilibrium configuration; F_e is a force rendering the static electro-elastic response of the DEGs; F_v is a rate-dependent contribution due to the DE material viscoelasticity; F_b is a static force due to the NBS; and F_{exc} is the external excitation force. F_e , F_v and F_b are calculated based on energy-preserving approaches, as described in the following.

2.2.1 DEG electro-elastic model The static electro-elastic force F_e of the DEG system is the sum of the contributions of the single units:

$$F_e = F_{e1} + F_{e2}, \quad (2)$$

where subscripts 1 and 2 indicate the bottom and top cone DEGs in Fig. 1b-c respectively. The static response of each unit is given as follows:

$$F_{ei} = \frac{dU_{el,i}}{dx} - 0.5V_i^2 \frac{dC_i}{dx}, \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) comes from an energy balance on the DEG unit (see [2] for derivation), where the first term represents the derivative of the DE elastic energy, $U_{el,i}$, and the second term is a co-energy, which accounts for the variations of the DE electrostatic internal energy and the contribution of the power supplied/absorbed by the power electronics, with V_i representing the applied voltage and C_i the capacitance of the i -th unit.

The DE mechanical response is modelled in a lumped fashion, assuming that the stretches are uniform over the membrane [14], and that the DE is a hyperelastic incompressible material [15]. For each DEG ($i = 1, 2$), we thus introduce a strain-

FIGURE 1: Layout of the dual-cone bistable DEG. (a) Single unit pre-stretching; (b) Dual-DEG equilibrium configuration; (c) Generic deformed configuration; (d) Four-phase working cycle for the two DEG units.

FIGURE 2: Schematic model of the viscoelastic material response

energy density Ψ_i , which is a function of the material stretches:

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_{el,i} &= \pi n_l \lambda_p^{-2} (r_o^2 - r_i^2) t_0 \Psi_i, \\
 \Psi_i &= C_{1,0} (I_{1,i} - 3) + C_{2,0} (I_{1,i} - 3)^2 + C_{3,0} (I_{1,i} - 3)^3 \quad (4) \\
 I_{1,i} &= \lambda_{1,i}^2 + \lambda_{2,i}^2 + (\lambda_{1,i} \lambda_{2,i})^{-2}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda_{1,i}$ and $\lambda_{2,i}$ are the principal stretches on the DE membrane surface in the meridian and circumferential direction respectively, whereas the stretch in the thickness direction is $\lambda_{3,i} = (\lambda_{1,i} \lambda_{2,i})^{-1}$ owing to incompressibility. Here, a hyperelastic model in Yeoh form is assumed, whose constitutive parameters are denoted $C_{1,0}$, $C_{2,0}$ and $C_{3,0}$. Similar to previous works [14], the stretches are calculated by assuming that the deformed DE

membrane has the shape of a truncated cone, and they read as follow:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda_{1,i} &= \lambda_p \frac{\sqrt{(r_o - r_i)^2 + [x + (-1)^i x_0]^2}}{r_o - r_i}, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (5) \\
 \lambda_{2,1} &= \lambda_{2,2} = \lambda_p,
 \end{aligned}$$

where x_0 is the off-plane displacement of the DEGs in the central equilibrium position.

The DEG capacitance for the two units ($i = 1, 2$) reads as follows:

$$C_i(x) = \frac{\epsilon_r \epsilon_0 n_l \pi}{t_0} (r_o - r_i) \left\{ (r_o - r_i)^2 + [x + (-1)^i x_0]^2 \right\} \quad (6)$$

where $\epsilon_0 = 8.85 \cdot 10^{-12}$ F/m is vacuum permittivity, and ϵ_r is the DE relative permittivity.

Notice that increasing x leads to an increase in C_1 and a decrease in C_2 . We assume that the voltage on each DEG is driven according to a four-phase cycle (Fig. 1d): 1) no voltage is applied on a DEG while its capacitance is increasing; 2) when the DEG capacitance reaches a maximum, the DEG is rapidly charged, i.e., an amount of electrical energy is preliminarily spent; 3) a certain (controlled) amount of voltage is applied on a DEG while its capacitance is decreasing: in this phase, mechanical work is spent to increase the electrostatic energy within the DEG, and a net amount of electrical energy is positively generated; 4) eventually, when a DEG reaches minimum capacitance, it is rapidly

discharged, and the stored energy is recovered. Notice that, in a complete oscillation of the disc, each DEG performs a complete generation cycle, with the two cycles being in phase opposition (phase 1) for unit 1 corresponds to phase 4) for unit 2). Here, we assume that, during phase 3), a constant electric field, $E_i = E_{BD}$, equal to the the material break-down limit E_{BD} , is applied on the DEG. The electric field E_i on any of the DEGs is related to the voltage as follows:

$$E_i = \lambda_{1,i} \lambda_{2,i} V_i / t_0. \quad (7)$$

Using Eqs. 2 and 3, the energy generated by the whole DEG system in an full cycle is :

$$\mathcal{E}_g = \oint (F_{b1} + F_{b2}) dx = -0.5 \oint (V_1^2 dC_1 + V_2^2 dC_2), \quad (8)$$

where the contribution of the elastic energy has been omitted from the right hand term, as it equals zero on a full cycle.

2.2.2 DEG viscoelastic model Similar to the static contribution, the DEG viscous force is the sum of two terms for the two units:

$$F_v = F_{v1} + F_{v2}. \quad (9)$$

These terms are calculated using the rheological model described in [11, 16]. The DE's viscoelasticity is modelled via two branches holding a damper with viscous coefficient η_{v0} , and a series of an elastic element (with stiffness k_v) and a damper (with viscous coefficient η_v), in parallel to the static elastic component (already described in Sect. 2.2.1), as schematically shown in Fig. 2. The resulting visco-elastic force components (for $i = 1, 2$) read as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{v,i} = & \pi n_l \lambda_p^{-2} (r_o^2 - r_i^2) t_0 \frac{d\lambda_{1,i}}{dx} \left(\frac{\partial \Psi_{v,i}}{\partial \lambda_{1,i}} + \frac{\partial \Psi_{v,i}}{\partial \xi_{v,i}} \right) + \\ & \pi n_l \lambda_p^{-2} (r_o^2 - r_i^2) t_0 \frac{\eta_{v0}}{\lambda_{1,i}} \left(\frac{d\lambda_{1,i}}{dx} \right)^2 \dot{x}, \quad (10) \\ \Psi_{v,i} = & k_v \left[\xi_{v,i} - (\lambda_{1,i} - \xi_{v,i}) \log \left(\frac{\lambda_{1,i}}{\lambda_{1,i} - \xi_{v,i}} \right) \right], \end{aligned}$$

where $\xi_{v,i}$ is a strain associated with the elastic branch of the viscoelastic model, and $\Psi_{v,i}$ is an energy storage function associated to the viscoelastic branches of the i -th DEG. Strain $\xi_{v,i}$ is described by the following dynamics:

$$\dot{\xi}_{v,i} = -\frac{k_v}{\eta_v} \xi_{v,i} + \frac{d\lambda_{1,i}}{dx} \dot{x} \quad (11)$$

TABLE 1: Parameters used in the simulations

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
r_o	35 mm	r_i	12.5 mm
t_0	50 μ m	n_l	4
λ_p	1.2	x_0	12 mm
C_{10}	183 kPa	C_{20}	14 kPa
C_{30}	34 kPa	k_v	400 kPa
η_v	350 kPa·s	η_{v0}	30 kPa·s
ϵ_r	2.8	E_{BD}	110 MV/m
m	10 g (bistable) 435 g (monost. reson.)		
l_0	25 mm	l	19.2 mm
k_s	12 kN/m		

2.2.3 NBS model The NBS is modelled as a set of in-parallel pre-compressed springs with total stiffness k_b . The springs have initial length l_0 and length l (with $l < l_0$) in the pre-compressed (unstable) configuration (see Fig. 1c). Force F_b is equal to the derivative of the NBS's elastic energy with respect to x , and it reads as follows:

$$F_b = k_b \left(1 - \frac{l_0}{\sqrt{l^2 + x^2}} \right) x \quad (12)$$

In the neighborhood of $x = 0$, $F_b \simeq -k_b(l_0/l - 1)x$, i.e., the force-stroke response of the spring is negative, with stiffness coefficient of $-k_b(l_0/l - 1)$.

3 SIMULATION RESULTS

We consider a dual-DEG with the features listed in Tab. 1. We assume the DEGs are made of a silicone elastomeric film (Elastosil 2030 by Wacker [17]). This materials is purposely developed for DE applications, it features significantly longer cyclic lifetime than other DEs (hence representing a serious candidate for future commercial DE applications) [18], but it is scarcely used in DEGs [19], because of its large elastic stiffness, which prevents the achievement of large deformation in many applications.

The system has radial dimensions on the order of centimetres and it features 0.46 g of active DE material (assuming a density of 1 g/cm³). The visco-elastic parameters are the same as those observed in [20] (re-fitted to a Yeoh form) for DE samples subject to large strains. The break-down electric field is compatible with measurements on the stretched material [21].

We hereby assume that the DEG is directly driven by an external force (e.g., generated by the interaction with an external

FIGURE 3: (a) Force-stroke response of the dual-cone DEG (with no electrical activation, and with the single DEGs activated with an electric field equal to E_{BD}) and the NBS system. (b) Total force-stroke response of the bistable DEG with NB.

source of mechanical energy) and we investigate the influence of the excitation frequency and magnitude on the energy extraction performance. We remark that, in some applications, the DEG might be installed on a moving frame (machine, human body) and driven by inertial forces induced on the moving disc. In this case, the magnitude of the excitation force would depend on the disc mass m (i.e., the system should be purposely provided with sufficient inertial mass) and the excitation frequency.

We consider and compare two distinct scenarios: 1) bistable embodiment, in which the DEG pair is coupled to a NBS (see Tab. 1), and the moving disc has small mass (compatible with the structural mass required to implement the mechanical connections); and 2) monostable resonant embodiment, in which no NBS is present, and the system is provided with a large moving mass, so as to resonate at a frequency of 10 Hz. Notice that, in the latter case, the required mass is over 40 times larger than that of the bistable case, and it would increase with quadratic trend, if lower resonance frequencies were sought.

The response of the DEG pair (without NBS, as considered in the monostable resonant case) with no voltage applied, and with an electric field equal to E_{BD} applied on either of the units is shown in Fig. 3a. The area comprised in between the limits curves (with maximum field on either of the DEG units) is the maximum energy convertible by the system within the considered stroke range. The response of the NBS is shown in dotted line in Fig. 3a (with reverted sign, so as to highlight the intersection points with the DEG response, which are equilibrium points for the bistable system), and the response of the combined system (DEGs + NBS) is shown in Fig. 3b. The system response shows a typical bistable behavior, with $x = 0$ representing an unstable equilibrium point (with negative slope of the force-stroke response) and two symmetrical stable equilibria in the range $x = \pm(8.8 \div 9.8)$ mm (depending on the electric

field). If the system is in one of the static equilibrium positions and it is pushed towards the opposite equilibrium point with a sufficiently large force (i.e., above a threshold of approximately 10 N, assuming the DEG on which a compression is applied is charged), the moving disc performs a bistable transition (i.e., a jump) from a static equilibrium point to the other, following a rapid dynamics.

In the following, we investigate the DEG performance in the presence of two different excitation waveforms: 1) sinusoidal excitation; and 2) multichromatic stochastic excitation. For the simulations, we coded dynamic model (1) into Simulink (through a block diagram with a structure qualitatively similar to that in Fig. 4), using a variable-step solver (*ode23t*). The static force-stroke of the DEG (passive, and in the presence of a constant electric field equal to E_{BD} on either of the DEG units - Fig. 3b) was implemented using look-up tables. The dynamics of the DEG moving mass (Eq. (1)), visco-elastic dynamics (11) and the control logics described in Sect. 2.2.1 were implemented via user-defined Matlab function objects.

3.1 Sinusoidal excitation

In this section, we assume that the DEG system is subject to an excitation force of the form:

$$F_{exc}(t) = F_0 \sin(2\pi ft), \quad (13)$$

where F_0 renders the excitation amplitude and f the frequency. Considering different combinations of the excitation parameters and calculating the electrical energy extracted by the system in a period (full oscillation) in steady-state conditions leads to the results shown in Fig. 5. For a given F_0 , the cyclic generated energy for the monostable resonant case is maximum in the neigh-

FIGURE 4: Block-diagram representing the model structure implementation.

borhood of $f = 10$ Hz, i.e., the nominal resonance frequency, where maximum deformation is achieved. The energy generated by the bistable design is nearly constant in the low-frequency range (quasi-static operation) and then decreases as the dynamics are dominated by damping. In the presence of low amplitude excitation (i.e., $F_0 = 6$ N - Fig. 5a), the monostable resonant implementation converts more energy than the bistable one. This happens because the excitation force is below the threshold requested to allow the system performing bistable jumps (see Fig. 3b), and the system oscillations remain confined above one of the static equilibrium positions. The time history of the DEGs displacement for a frequency $f = 1$ Hz is shown in Fig. 6a. As explained, whereas the monostable DEG oscillates above $x = 0$, the bistable oscillator stays in the neighborhood of one of the static equilibria. Because, the stiffness of the system (i.e., the slope of the force-stroke curves in Fig. 3b) in such remote equilibria is larger than the monostable system's stiffness at $x = 0$, the bistable implementation features smaller oscillation amplitudes and, hence, lower energy output.

If the excitation amplitude is sufficiently large (e.g., $F_0 = 12$ N - Fig. 5b), the bistable embodiment experiments periodic jumps between the two equilibria in a broad low-frequency range. In this case, the energy generated by the bistable DEG at low frequencies is approximately twice the energy extracted by the corresponding resonant implementation, with the latter offering better performance only in a narrow range around resonance. The time histories of the DEG displacement at $f = 1$ Hz (Fig. 6b) show that the bistable DEG performs quick jumps between the equilibrium points, and overall achieves significantly larger displacements than its resonant counterpart. In the higher frequency range (over 10 Hz), the energy output of the bistable oscillator experiments a significant drop, as the viscous dynamics prevent the DEG from experimenting bistable jumps, and oscillations are again confined above one of the equilibria. By further increasing the excitation amplitude ($F_0 = 18$ N - Fig. 5c), the range in which the bistable design performs bistable jumps increases. The monostable embodiment generates a lower amount of energy (ex-

cept for a narrow range around resonance) even though the percentage difference at low frequencies is now lower compared to the case $F_0 = 12$ N. The time histories of the displacement (Fig. 6c) show that the displacement reached by the bistable design is close to that achieved with lower applied force (i.e., $F_0 = 12$ N), whereas the monostable DEG displacement is sensibly increased. The energy harvested per cycle by the bistable design at low frequency is therefore close to that of the previous scenario (cf. Figs. 5b and c), whereas the performance of the monostable implementation visibly increases with F_0 . In practice, because the bistable DEG has a rather large stiffness outside of the range identified by the stable equilibrium positions, its low-frequency oscillations are roughly confined in between such positions and weakly depend on F_0 (provided that this is above a certain threshold).

A comparison of the steady-state state-space trajectories of the DEGs, at $f = 1$ Hz and different values of F_0 for the two cases (bistable and monostable) is shown in Fig. 7, in terms of the DEG displacement x and the total force of the DEG system (F_e for the monostable system, $F_e + F_b$ for the bistable one, which are evaluated using Eqs. (2)-(3)). The area enclosed by the trajectories equals the energy converted in a cycle (as reported in Fig. 5). As discussed above, increasing F_0 above a certain threshold (which triggers bistable jumps) leads to a remarkable increase in the DEG performance, and allows exploiting almost the entire working range of the DEGs (between the limit curves). In the monostable implementation, the converted energy increases in a nearly-proportional way with F_0 (i.e., large F_0 is required to achieve large cyclic convertible energy). The energy density converted at $f = 1$ Hz and $F_0 = 18$ N is 0.23 kJ/kg for the bistable DEG and 0.16 kJ/kg for the monostable one (though the latter reaches a peak value of 0.28 kJ/kg at resonance).

3.2 Stochastic excitation

We now investigate the performance of the DEG system subject to multichromatic stochastic excitations, expressed as a sum of sinusoidal components. We define a spectrum, $S_\omega(\omega)$, with $\omega = 2\pi f$ denoting the angular frequency, such that:

$$\int_0^\infty S_\omega(\omega) d\omega \simeq \sum_{k=1}^N S_\omega(\omega_k) = 1, \quad (14)$$

where the set $\{\omega_i : i = 1, \dots, N\}$ represents a discretisation of the frequency axis (with constant spacing $\Delta\omega = \omega_i - \omega_{i-1}$), in a finite range outside of which $S_\omega \simeq 0$. We then express the excitation force as a finite sum of harmonic terms:

$$F_{exc}(t) = F_0 \sum_{k=1}^N \sqrt{S_\omega(\omega_k) \Delta\omega} \sin(\omega_k t + \phi_k), \quad (15)$$

FIGURE 5: Electrical energy generated per cycle, as a function of the frequency, for different sinusoidal excitation amplitudes: (a) $F_0 = 6N$, (b) $F_0 = 12N$, (c) $F_0 = 18N$

FIGURE 6: Time history of the DEGs' displacement x for a sinusoidal excitation with frequency $f = 1$ Hz and three different amplitudes: (a) $F_0 = 6N$, (b) $F_0 = 12N$, (c) $F_0 = 18N$

where F_0 is an excitation coefficient and $\phi_i \in [0, 2\pi]$ are randomly distributed phases. Notice that, with this definition, F_{exc} in (15) has the same energy (in the sense of signal theory, i.e., the root-mean-square value) as a sinusoidal force with amplitude F_0 . Similar approaches are used to generate the timeseries of multichromatic excitation force profiles on marine structures subject to stochastic waves [22]. Here, we consider excitation spectra in Weibull form:

$$S_\omega(\omega) = \frac{k_s}{\alpha} \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha} \right)^{k_s-1} e^{-(\omega/\alpha)^{k_s}}, \quad (16)$$

where k_s is a shape parameter (here, $k_s = 10$ is used), and α is a scale parameter, suitably chosen so as to obtain a target peak frequency $\omega_p = 2\pi f_p$ (in correspondence of which S_ω is maximum). Fig. 8a shows the shape of the spectrum for $f_p = 1$ Hz and Fig. 8b shows an example of the corresponding excitation force trend for $F_0 = 12$ N.

We evaluate the response of the DEG system to multichromatic excitation (15) by running simulations on a long time hori-

zon (with length of $400/f_p$), evaluating the total converted energy, and calculating an average cyclic converted energy based on the average frequency of the spectrum. Simulations are repeated for different excitations, characterized by different combinations of f_p and F_0 , and the resulting trends of the average generated cyclic energy are shown in Fig. 9. The generated energy is on the same order as that obtained in monochromatic conditions (Fig. 5) at the same frequency and same excitation amplitude, even though here the generated energy is systematically lower than in the sinusoidal scenario. Similar to the monochromatic scenario, the monostable resonant implementation converts the maximum energy in the presence of peak frequencies close to the system resonance frequency. In contrast with the monochromatic case (Fig. 5a), here the advantage of the monostable implementation at low excitation amplitudes and low frequencies is marginal. Similar to the case with monochromatic excitation, in the low frequency range the bistable system converts more energy than the monostable one for excitation amplitudes of $F_0 = 12$ and 18 N (Fig. 9b and c).

FIGURE 7: State-space trajectories (stroke vs total DEG force) corresponding to the datasets in Fig. 5. (a) Bistable DEG, (b) Monostable resonant DEG.

Whereas in the presence of monochromatic excitations, the percentage energy advantage of the bistable DEG over the monostable one is higher for intermediate excitation forces close to the threshold required to trigger the jumps (cf. Fig. 5b and c), here the difference in performance between bistable and monostable is similar for the two cases with $F_0 = 12$ N and $F_0 = 18$ N (in both cases, the bistable layout produces, in average, 55-60% more energy).

Fig. 10 shows the time-series of the DEG displacement (top row) and the corresponding cumulative generated electrical energy (bottom row), for both the monostable and bistable implementations, in case of a stochastic excitation with $f_p = 1$ Hz and different amplitudes. The harvested energy (Fig. 10 - bottom) is here calculated as the cumulative time integral of the integrand on the right-hand-side of Eq. (8), and it is set equal to zero at the beginning of each plot for comparison. Owing to the stochastic nature of the excitation, the bistable system performs a number of bistable jumps even in the presence of a relatively low average excitation amplitude ($F_0 = 6$, Fig. 10a-top). In this case ($F_0 = 6$), the bistable implementation generates less energy than the monostable one in the time intervals where no jumps occur, and a significantly larger amount of energy in those intervals where bistability is triggered, leading to comparable total energy yields in the two cases. As the excitation amplitude increases

(Fig. 10b and c), the percentage time during which the bistable system undergoes jumps increases (even though there still exist time intervals where the system oscillations are confined above one of the stable equilibria), leading to larger converted energies than in the monostable case.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a simulation study on a bistable dielectric elastomer generators. A well-known drawback of DEGs is associated to the stiffness of the dielectric elastomeric material, which prevents a DEG from achieving large deformations (and, hence, convert large amounts of energy) unless large excitation forces are applied, and requires a large amount of mechanical reactive power be involved in the DEG dynamics. An approach to overcome this issue and match the DEG mechanical impedance with the available mechanical energy sources consists in resorting to resonant designs, i.e., tuning the natural frequency of the DEG (and the coupled interfaces) with some relevant excitation frequency. Besides requiring large inertial loads, however, resonant designs experiment a drastic reduction in performance when operating off-resonance, and are therefore unsuitable to operate over large frequency ranges. The use of bistable designs, capable of undergoing large deformations in between a couple of stable equilibrium points, represents a possible alternative approach. In this work we consider a silicone-based DEG system based on an agonist-antagonist DEG pair. We present a dynamic model of the system, based on previously validated electro-visco-elastic models, and perform simulation studies to investigate the potential of a bistable implementation (obtained by coupling the DEG pair with a negative-stiffness spring) against a traditional monostable resonant design (obtained by coupling the DEGs with a mass). Simulation results prove that resorting to a bistable behavior leads to an improvement in the cyclic converted energy at low frequencies, provided that the excitation force surpasses a minimum threshold (required to trigger bistable jumps). This trend holds true both in the presence of monochromatic sinusoidal excitation forces, and stochastic excitations given by the superposition of multiple harmonic terms with random phases and amplitudes distributed according to a spectrum. The results presented in this paper are a first theoretical analysis aimed at highlighting the potential of bistable DEG architectures. However, a number of open problems need to be addressed in order to allow transferring the presented concepts in the practice. Among other, these include the design of suitable power electronics and control logics able to handle the quick transients (and the large amount of energy consequently released) associated with bistable jumps.

FIGURE 8: (a) Example of (a) excitation spectrum and (b) corresponding excitation force waveform for $f_p = 1$ Hz and $F_0 = 12$ N

FIGURE 9: Electrical energy generated per cycle (average), as a function of the peak frequency, for different spectral excitation amplitudes: (a) $F_0 = 6$ N, (b) $F_0 = 12$ N, (c) $F_0 = 18$ N

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FIGURE 10: Extracts of the time histories of the DEGs’ displacement x (top row) and the cumulative generated electrical energy (bottom row) for a spectral excitation with peak frequency $f_p = 1$ Hz and three different amplitudes: (a) $F_0 = 6N$, (b) $F_0 = 12N$, (c) $F_0 = 18N$

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